

water and finally extracted with benzene. The benzene extract on tlc plate gave three spots in benzene-ethyl acetate (80 : 20) solvent system. These extracts were further washed with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (to remove the acidic part), then with water and finally dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The dried extracts after removal of benzene were treated with petroleum ether and kept in a refrigerator to provide a solid which was separated by filtration. The solid was treated with ethanol when it dissolved partially.

The alcohol-soluble part gave white crystals of flavone (1.93 g), m.p. 99–100° (lit.⁵ 99°). The identity of the flavone was (3a) further confirmed by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra ($C=O$, 1644 cm^{-1}) with the authentic sample of flavone. The alcohol-insoluble part gave yellow, nitrogen containing product (0.38 g) when crystallised from benzene, which was identified as flavanone azine (4a), m.p. 256–58° (Found: C, 81.5; H, 5.9; N, 6.0. $C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires: C, 81.0; H, 5.4; N, 6.3%); ν_{max} 1617 cm^{-1} (conjugated $C=O$); nmr ($CDCl_3$) showed multiplets at δ 6.9–7.1 (CH_2 quartet), 4.6–4.8 (CH quartet) due to spin-spin interaction with each other, 2.5–3.1 (9H, Ar) and 7.5–8.3 (CH_2), 6.1–6.6 (OCH_3) (only in substituted azines). Other flavanone hydrazones (1b–f) when similarly oxidised gave similar products, viz. corresponding flavones (3b–f) and flavanone azines (4b–f) and have also been characterised by ir, nmr, m.m.p., elemental analysis and molecular weight determination (Rast).

The sodium bicarbonate washings collected from all the six reaction mixtures when neutralised with dilute HCl provided a white solid which on crystallisation from hot water gave salicylic acid (2), m.p. 156° (lit.⁶ 156°) in each case.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. B. V. Singh, Principal, for facilities, and authorities of D.R.D.E., Gwalior, for spectral data. One of the authors (A.S.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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Synthesis and Evaluation of AChE Inhibitory Activity of 5-Substituted-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione-3-[(6*H*/bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinyl)]hydrazones

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Manuscript received 12 August 1986, revised 10 February 1987,
accepted 7 August 1987

QUINAZOLINES have been found to exhibit marked pharmacological activity, such as CNS depressant¹, anticonvulsant², AChE^{3,4}, anti-allergic⁵ and antiviral⁶. The indole nucleus has also been known to display multifarious biological activity. Prompted by these reports, the synthesis of new compounds was undertaken in which quinazoline nucleus was incorporated with an indole nucleus through a hydrazo linkage.

The present study deals with the synthesis of 5-substituted-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione-3-[(6*H*/bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinyl)]hydrazones.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in an electrical melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Structures of the compounds were verified by ir spectra, recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. The pmr spectra were taken on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Purity of all the compounds was checked on silica gel G plates using iodine vapour as visualising agent.

6*H*/Bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoquinazoline-2-hydrazines (1a–f): The compounds were prepared from corresponding 6*H*/bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoquinazoline-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-r

Compd. no.	R	R'	R''	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
3a	H	H	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	314	61	18.40 (18.37)
3b	H	H	Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	291	64	16.78 (16.84)
3c	H	H	Me	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	290	64	17.65 (17.7)
3d	H	Me	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	295	66	17.72 (17.7)
3e	H	Me	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	300	63	16.22 (16.29)
3f	H	Me	Me	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂	295	62	17.07 (17.11)
3g	H	Cl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	282	60	16.78 (16.84)
3h	H	Cl	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	283	60	15.63 (15.59)
3i	H	Cl	Me	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	275	67	16.35 (16.29)
3j	Br	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Br	257	63	15.14 (15.21)
3k	Br	H	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl	274	64	14.09 (14.15)
3l	Br	H	Me	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Br	27	65	14.68 (14.76)
3m	Br	Me	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Br	293	61	14.72 (14.76)
3n	Br	Me	Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl	300	67	13.71 (13.76)
3o	Br	Me	Me	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br	284	65	14.28 (14.34)
3p	Br	Cl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl	285	62	14.06 (14.15)
3q	Br	Cl	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl ₂	294	64	13.21 (13.25)
3r	Br	Cl	Me	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ BrCl	280	66	13.73 (13.76)

2-thiols by the method of Gianturco *et al.*⁷ and have been reported in the lab previously.

5-Methyl-1H-indole-2,3-dione 3-[6H-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-methylphenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinyl]hydrazone (3f) : **1b** (2 g, 0.007 mol) was taken in alcohol and refluxed for 0.5 h. Methyl isatin (1.12 g, 0.007 mol) was then added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. Solvent was removed by distillation and the resulting solid was cooled, filtered and washed with a little alcohol. The compound was recrystallised from DMF, (2 g, 66.6%), m.p. 294° (Found : C, 70.45 ; H, 4.62 ; N, 17.00. C₂₄H₁₉N₂O₂ requires : C, 70.41 ; H, 4.64, N, 17.11%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 690 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH) ; δ 2.2 (6H, s, CH₃), 5.6 (1H, s, NH of indole), 5.9 (1H, s, NH), 6.8-8.1 (11H, m, Ar-H).

Similarly, 17 more compounds were synthesised (Table 1).

Acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity : Acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity was determined on rat brain homogenate using acetylthiocholine as the substrate at 5 × 10⁻⁵ M concentration. The thiocholine formed by the enzymatic hydrolysis of acetylthiocholine was determined colorimetrically. The decrease in thiocholine formation in experiments

containing synthetic compounds was taken as the index of enzyme inhibition.

The compounds did not show any marked inhibitory activity. Further work on biological activity is being carried out.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head of Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, for facilities. Authors are also thankful to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for analytical facilities. One of the authors (S.A.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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One-pot Conversion of 2-Methyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one into 3-Substituted-2-styrylquinazolin-4-ones

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Manuscript received 2 March 1987, accepted 7 August 1987

QUINAZOLIN-4-ones are important class of compounds and their chemistry continues to be of considerable interest¹⁻³. In connection with our studies in heterocycles carrying an activated methyl group, the title reaction was investigated. The synthesis of **5** is usually carried out in a stepwise fashion¹, but in the present method, all the steps were carried out in the same flask (see Experimental). Products were characterised by ¹H nmr data, which ruled out the alternative structure **6**, and these were confirmed by comparison with authentic samples. The relevant physical constants are given in Table 1. The amides (**3**), which are the precursors of **4**, however, could not be isolated.

dryness under reduced pressure and the resulting compound (**2**) was treated with a primary amine (1.1 mol) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml/g of **1**). An aromatic aldehyde (1.1 mol) was then added to the mixture and refluxed for ~2.5 h using freshly fused sodium acetate as a catalyst. It was concentrated to dryness over a steam-bath and the crude product

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-SUBSTITUTED-2-STYRYLQUINAZOLIN-4-ONES (**5**)

Compd. no.	R	Ar	Yield ^a %	M.p. ^{**} °C	δ (ppm) (CDCl ₃ /TMS)
5a	Ph	Ph	60	198 ^a	6.25 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhOH=CH), 7.09–7.68 (12H, m, Ar-H), 7.81 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhCH=CH), 8.18 (2H, d, Ar-H)
5b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	61	201 ^b	6.28 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhOH=CH), 7.06–7.72 (11H, m, Ar-H), 7.97 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz, PhCH=CH), 8.18 (2H, d, Ar-H)
5c	4-MeO-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	60	220 ^a	3.88 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.46 (1H, d, J 16.4 Hz, PhOH=CH), 7.00–7.83 (11H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, J 16.4 Hz, PhCH=CH), 8.30 (2H, d, Ar-H)
5d	4-HOOC-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	59	285 ^c	Insufficiently soluble
5e	Ph	2-HO-C ₆ H ₄	47	269 ^a	Insufficiently soluble
5f	2-HOOC-C ₆ H ₄	3,4-MeO, HO-C ₆ H ₄	45	205 ^c	Insufficiently soluble

^aBased on *N*-acetylanthranilic acid taken. ^{**}Lit. reference ^aRef. 4, ^bRef. 5, ^cRef. 2.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL 90Q spectrophotometer.

3-Substituted 2-styrylquinazolin-4-ones (5); General procedure: To a suspension of *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (**1**; 1.0 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml/g of the acid) containing triethylamine (2.2 mol), tosylchloride (1.01 mol) was added and the mixture shaken for a few min at room temperature. Triethylamine salts were filtered off and washed with dry benzene. The filtrate was concentrated to

was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give a pure compound. The physical data are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University, for the award of a Research Fellowship to one of them (A.J.).

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